

A Best Worst Prioritization Method under a 2-tuple Linguistic Environment in Decision Making Problems

Álvaro Labella^a, Bapi Dutta^b, Luis Martínez^a

^a*University of Jaén, Department of Computer Science, Jaén, Spain*

^b*The Logistics Institute—Asia Pacific, National University of Singapore, 21 Heng Mui Keng Terrace, 119613, Singapore*

Abstract

Multi-criteria group decision making (MCGDM) deals with the process of making decision among a set of decision makers who evaluate alternatives over several criteria. MCGDM problems evolve in tandem with the progress of society and thus, their complexity is growing. Such complexity has given rise to the large-scale group decision making (LS-GDM) problems in which hundreds of decision makers may participate in the decision process and there are challenges to face such as groups formation and polarization opinions. In any MCGDM problem, the elicitation of decision makers' preferences is a key task, because the solution of the problem is determined by this information. Pairwise comparison is a widely used technique for this task but, a large number of comparisons might lead to erroneous solutions, since the consistency of the decision makers' preferences could be affected. The best-worst method (BWM) was proposed in order to reduce the number of comparisons and consequently, the apparition of inconsistency in decision makers' opinions. However, this proposal deals with numerical assessments, which are not enough to model uncertainty that commonly appears in MCGDM problems. To face the latter limitation, an extension to the fuzzy environment of the BWM was proposed, taking advantage of the use of linguistic information and of its well performance in uncertainty modelling. Nevertheless, the latter proposal represented the results by means of triangular fuzzy membership functions, which are hard to understand from decision makers' point of view. Therefore, in this study, we extend the classic BWM in the 2-tuple linguistic environment to model uncertainty associated with the pairwise judgments/comparisons via fuzzy linguistic terms and to enhance the accuracy of computation over linguistic terms and interpretability of the results. Moreover, we apply our proposal to LS-GDM scenarios in which polarization opinions and sub-groups identification that, so far, have not been addressed from any of BWM proposals, are taken into account.

Keywords: Best-worst method, 2-tuple linguistic model, Group decision making, optimal group formation

*Corresponding author

Email addresses: alabella@ujaen.es (Álvaro Labella), bapi.iitr@gmail.com (Bapi Dutta), martin@ujaen.es (Luis Martínez)

1. Introduction

Decision making (DM) is a common daily task for human beings. Either because of the increasing complexity of the decisions or the need to consider different points of view for making the decision, *Group decision making* (GDM) has become a fundamental activity in our society. GDM problems are defined as decision situations in which several decision makers, $\{e_1, \dots, e_s\}$, with their own attitudes try to reach a common solution to a problem consisting of two or more possible solutions or alternatives, $\{x_1, \dots, x_m\}$. Decision makers may evaluate the alternatives according to different and usually conflicting criteria, $\{C_1, \dots, C_n\}$, giving rise to *multi-criteria group decision making* (MCGDM). DM is constantly evolving and the apparition of technological advances such as social network [1] and big data [2] or social needs such as e-markets [3] has resulted in a new type of GDM problems, so-called *large-scale group decision making* (LS-GDM) problems, in which hundreds or thousands of decision makers may be involved in the decision process [4–7]. LS-GDM problems present novel challenges to face respect to the classical GDM problems such as the decision makers' polarization opinions [8]. Polarization in opinions is quite common in LS-GDM and such polarized views have to be identified in order to understand the proper dynamics of groups with a large number of stakeholders/participants [9, 10]. There might not have any unanimous agreement/view towards an alternative but there might have multiple sub-groups and each sub-group agreed unanimously on a ranking of the set of alternatives.

The decision makers' preferences elicitation is a fundamental pillar in any DM problem. *Pairwise comparison* method proposed by Thurstone [11] is a widely used technique for the decision makers' preferences elicitation, which has been applied in popular MCGDM methods such as the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) [12]. However, it is impossible to neglect the inconsistency in pairwise comparison matrices [13], which might be the cause of wrong results. Inconsistency in decision makers' opinions often takes place when there are a large number of criteria or alternatives, since the numbers of pairwise comparison increases and, consequently, the complexity of solving MCGDM problems. Keeping in mind the latter limitation, Rezaei proposed in [14] a new MCGDM method to obtain the prioritization of the objects (alternatives and/or criteria) in a DM problem, so-called *best-worst Method* (BWM), which uses fewer comparison data by establishing a new structure of making pairwise comparisons. This new structure consists of comparing only the best and the worst element of the problem, both selected by the decision makers, with the rest of them. In this way, it is not necessary to compare all the elements with each other and the inherent inconsistency of the pairwise comparisons is reduced when the number of criteria or alternatives is too large. Further, several optimization models [14–16] have been put forwarded in the literature to derive the priority weights from the reference comparisons of the best-worst objects with the rest of objects. However, there is no guideline and comparison analysis of these approaches to infer which one is the best on the aspect of preserving the decision maker's given preference.

The BWM proposed by Rezaei [14] considers pairwise comparison matrices in which the human assessments are provided by crisp numbers (1-9 scale-based). However, real-world MCGDM problems present

vague and uncertain information that cannot be modeled by discrete values. In this realm, several proposals have been put forwarded by the researchers to accommodate different types of uncertainty within the framework of BWM [17–21]. In the same vein, Guo and Zhao introduced the *Fuzzy BWM* in [17], an extension of the BWM to the fuzzy environment to model the inherent uncertainty in many real-life decision scenarios. This proposal replaces the discrete pairwise comparison matrices with fuzzy comparing judgements represented by linguistic expressions, which facilitate the experts’ elicitation. Afterwards, linguistic expressions are transformed into triangular fuzzy numbers (TFNs) [22] by obtaining more reliable decision result. However, Fuzzy BWM provides results represented by fuzzy numbers, far from the initial linguistic information provided by the experts and difficult to understand.

Therefore, taking account the premises above, our contribution consists of a new extension of BWM under a *Computing with Words* [23–26] (CW) paradigm. The main characteristic of the CW paradigm is the obtaining of linguistic outcomes from linguistic inputs, obtaining results that are easily understandable and properly represented. Therefore, for our BWM proposal, decision makers provide their preferences by using fuzzy linguistic pairwise comparisons and results are also provided by linguistic information in order to facilitate their understanding. The 2-tuple linguistic model [27] is used to carry out the linguistic computations, because its precision and interpretability [28]. Furthermore, in order to evaluate the consistency of the decision makers’ preferences and avoid wrong results, a consistency ratio is proposed. Finally, note that all the BWM proposals obtain an unique preference ranking by minimizing the deviation of the given preference information from the group of decision makers, by ignoring the apparition of sub-groups and opinions polarization, which is quite common, for instance, in LS-GDM problems. Thus, our proposal also tries to come up with the multiple views and opinions polarization in LS-GDM. To sum up, our study aims to:

- Analyze and compare different prioritization approaches for BWM and select for our proposal the one that preserves as much as possible the initial decision makers’ preferences.
- Propose a new extension of the BWM, so-called 2-tuple BWM, which follows a CW approach by obtaining from fuzzy linguistic pairwise comparisons, linguistic results represented by 2-tuple linguistic values easily understandable and precise. Additionally, in order to facilitate the decision makers’ understanding of the preservation of the given linguistic preferences, the deviation from the original opinions is also translated into linguistic values.
- Propose a consistency ratio for the 2-tuple BWM proposal considering the average cognitive behaviour of the experts in order to detect the inconsistency in their preferences and avoid incorrect solutions.
- Apply the so-called 2-tuple BWM to LS-GDM problems in which the different attitudes and polarization of the opinions of the decision makers are taken into account to find out the proper dynamics of the group, facing one of the most relevant challenges in this type of problems.

To do this, the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 reviews some basic concepts about the BWM and the 2-tuple linguistic model in order to facilitate the understanding of the proposal. Section 3 introduces different approaches to compute the prioritization of the elements in a DM process. Section 4 presents the extension of the BWM for linguistic information based on the 2-tuple linguistic model and introduces a novel consistency measure. Section 5 extends the proposal to LS-GDM problems and deals with the apparition of sub-groups and opinions polarization. Section 6 shows different practical examples in order to show the performance and usefulness of the proposal for classical DM and LS-GDM problems. Finally, in Section 7 some concluding remarks are pointed out.

2. Preliminaries

This section reviews several concepts related to BWM and 2-tuple linguistic model in order to understand easily this contribution.

2.1. Best-worst method

BWM [14] is a MCGDM method that derives the criteria weights by reducing the number of pairwise comparisons among criteria. To do this, the best criterion C_B and the worst criterion C_W are predetermined by the experts and compared with the rest of the criteria. These comparisons are named as *reference comparison*. The steps that compose the BWM for the criteria weights computation are:

- **Step 1:** Determine a set of decision criteria.
- **Step 2:** Select the best criterion C_B and the worst criterion C_W . In case that there are several best and worst criteria, these can be selected arbitrary.
- **Step 3:** Make pairwise comparison among C_B and the rest of the criteria, by obtaining the Best to Others (BO) vector, $BO = \{a_{B1}, a_{B2}, \dots, a_{Bn}\}$, where B_j denotes the preference degree of C_B over the criterion C_j and $a_{Bj} \geq 1, j = 1, 2, \dots, n, j \neq B$.
- **Step 4:** Make pairwise comparison among C_W and the rest of the criteria, by obtaining the Worst to Others (WO) vector, $WO = \{a_{1W}, a_{2W}, \dots, a_{nW}\}$, where a_{jW} denotes the preference degree of the criterion C_j over C_W and $a_{jW} \geq 1, j = 1, 2, \dots, n, j \neq B$ or W .
- **Step 5:** Compute the weights of criteria by optimization models. For each reference comparison, the optimal weights of criteria satisfy $w_B/w_j = a_{Bj}$ and $w_j/w_W = a_{jW}$. Therefore, the maximum absolute differences $|w_B/w_j - a_{Bj}|$ and $|w_j/w_W - a_{jW}|$ should be minimized. Different prioritization approaches for BWM have been introduced in the literature, some of them have introduced in Section 3.

Note that Rezaei also introduced in [14] a consistency ratio for evaluating the consistency of the pairwise comparisons based on numerical scales. According to Rezaei proposal, a comparison is fully consistent when

$a_{Bj} \times a_{jW} = a_{BW}$ for all j , where a_{Bj} , a_{jW} and a_{BW} are respectively the preference of the best criterion over the criterion j , the preference of criterion j over the worst criterion, and the preference of the best criterion over the worst criterion. To indicate how consistent a comparison is, a *consistency ratio* is calculated as follows:

$$\text{Consistency Ratio} = \frac{\varepsilon^*}{\text{Consistency Index}} \quad (1)$$

where ε^* represents the maximum absolute difference among the optimal weights and the reference comparisons and *Consistency Index* is a numerical value obtained from a_{BW} (see [14] for further details).

Lately, an extension to the fuzzy environment of the BWM was proposed by Guo and Zhao in [17]. The biggest difference among the fuzzy extension and the original proposal is the use of fuzzy linguistic information in the reference comparisons. Experts provide their assessments by using linguistic expressions that are transformed subsequently into TFNs, (l, m, u) (see [17] for further detail).

2.2. 2-tuple Linguistic Model

There are several linguistic computational models based on the fuzzy linguistic approach to accomplish linguistic computations. However, in terms of interpretability and precision, the 2-tuple linguistic model proposed by Herrera and Martínez [27, 29] stands out from the rest of symbolic fuzzy based models [30]. This linguistic model, based on the concept of symbolic translation, represents the information by means of a 2-tuple, (s_i, α) , where s_i is a linguistic label belonging to a predefined linguistic term set $S = \{s_1, s_2 \dots s_g\}$ and $\alpha \in [-0.5, 0.5]$ a numerical value that represents the translation of the fuzzy membership function that represents the closest term s_i , if s_i does not match exactly the computed linguistic information (see Fig 1). The value of α is defined as:

$$\alpha = \begin{cases} [-0.5, 0.5) & \text{if } s_i \in \{s_1, s_2, \dots, s_{g-1}\} \\ [0, 0.5) & \text{if } s_i = s_0 \\ [-0.5, 0] & \text{if } s_i = s_g \end{cases}$$

Figure 1: Symbolic translation

The symbolic computation on linguistic terms in S returns a value $\beta \in [0, g]$, which is transformed into an equivalent 2-tuple linguistic value, (s_i, α) by means of the function Δ_S defined as follows:

Definition 1 ([27]). Let $S = \{s_0, \dots, s_g\}$ be a set of linguistic terms and \bar{S} the 2-tuple set associated with S defined as $\bar{S} = S \times [-0.5, 0.5)$. The function $\Delta_S : [0, g] \rightarrow \bar{S}$ is given by:

$$\Delta_S(\beta) = (s_i, \alpha), \text{ with } \begin{cases} i = \text{round}(\beta) \\ \alpha = \beta - i \end{cases}$$

with $\text{round}(\cdot)$ the function that assigns to β the closest integer number $i \in \{0, \dots, g\}$ to β .

Therefore, a 2-tuple linguistic value (s_i, α) can be represented by its equivalent numerical value β in the interval of granularity of S , $[0, g]$.

Proposition 1. Let $S = \{s_0, \dots, s_g\}$ be a linguistic term set and $(s_i, \alpha) \in \bar{S}$ be a 2-tuple linguistic value. There is a function, Δ^{-1} :

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta^{-1} : \bar{S} &\rightarrow [0, g] \\ \Delta_S^{-1}(s_i, \alpha) &= \alpha + i = \beta \end{aligned}$$

Remark 1. From Definition 1 and Proposition 1, the transformation of a linguistic term $s_i \in S$ into a 2-tuple linguistic value in \bar{S} is carried out by adding a zero as a symbolic translation to the linguistic term:

$$s_i \in S \rightarrow (s_i, 0) \in \bar{S}$$

Furthermore, the 2-tuple linguistic model has associated a computational model [27].

In later works [31], the 2-tuple linguistic model was extended in order to interpret values from the scale $[0, 1]$ rather than conventional scale $[0, g_1]$ corresponding to the linguistic term set $S_1 = \{s_0^1, s_1^1, \dots, s_{g_1}^1\}$. In such cases any value $\beta \in [0, 1]$ can be mapped to the 2-tuple linguistic terms set \bar{S}_1 via the mapping $\Delta_1 : [0, 1] \rightarrow \bar{S}_1 = S_1 \times [-\frac{1}{2g_1}, \frac{1}{2g_1})$.

Definition 2. [31] A value β whose value belongs to interval $[0, 1]$ will be obtained after aggregating the result of evaluation using the linguistic variable set S_1 . Then the symbolic translation process is applied to translate β into a 2-tuple linguistic variable. The generalized translation function (Δ_1) can be represented as

$$\Delta_1(\beta) = (s_i, \alpha) \text{ where } \begin{cases} s_i & i = \text{round}(\beta \cdot g_1) \\ \alpha = \beta - \frac{i}{g_1} & \alpha \in [-\frac{1}{2g_1}, \frac{1}{2g_1}) \end{cases}$$

Clearly the value of the symbolic translation depends on the cardinality of the linguistic term set S_1 . On the other hand, the 2-tuple representation from the 2-tuple information (s_i, α) could be translated into equivalent numerical value $\beta \in [0, 1]$ with the help of re-translation function $\Delta_1^{-1} : \bar{S}_1 \rightarrow [0, 1]$.

Definition 3. [31] A reverse equation Δ_1^{-1} is necessary to return an equivalent numerical value $\beta \in [0, 1] \subset \mathfrak{R}$ from a 2-tuple linguistic variable (s_i, α) . According to the concept of symbolic translation, an equivalent numerical value β is computed as

$$\Delta_1^{-1}(s_i, \alpha) = \beta = \frac{i}{g} + \alpha.$$

3. Prioritization approaches for best-worst method

One of the key issues associated with the BWM is the deriving the priority of the objects from the pairwise comparisons of the best and worst objects. Consequently, our proposal has to deal with this issue too. There are several approaches that allow us to obtain such priority but, they may provide different results. For this reason, it is necessary to analyse all these approaches and select properly the most suitable one for our proposal.

3.1. Prioritization process

To describe the prioritization process, we provide its' mathematical formalization as follows. Let $X = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ be the set of objects. We are going to denote the best and worst objects of X as x_B and x_W , respectively. Clearly, the indexes $B, W \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$. Next, the decision maker compares the best and worst objects with the rest of the objects in a pairwise fashion by using the numeric scale '1-9', where '1' represents the objects x_i and x_j are equally important and '9' represents that the object x_i is extremely important than x_j . The decision maker's pairwise preference could be summarized in the following matrix:

$$D = \begin{matrix} & \begin{matrix} x_1 & x_2 & \cdots & x_B & \cdots & x_W & \cdots & x_n \end{matrix} \\ \begin{matrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ \vdots \\ x_B \\ \vdots \\ x_n \end{matrix} & \begin{pmatrix} - & - & \cdots & - & \cdots & a_{1W} & \cdots & - \\ - & - & \cdots & - & \cdots & a_{2W} & \cdots & - \\ \vdots & \vdots & \cdots & \vdots & \cdots & \vdots & \cdots & \vdots \\ a_{B1} & a_{B2} & \cdots & - & \cdots & a_{BW} & \cdots & a_{Bn} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \cdots & \vdots & \cdots & \vdots & \cdots & \vdots \\ - & - & \cdots & - & \cdots & a_{nW} & \cdots & - \end{pmatrix} \end{matrix}$$

To determine the priority vector from the above pairwise comparison matrix different optimization models have been put forwarded in the literature. We describe them briefly in the following subsections.

3.1.1. Non-linear optimization models

In this approach, the priority weight vector $w = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n)$ is deriving from the pairwise preference matrix based on the principle of the minimization of the maximized deviation from the given preferences

and that can be put in the following optimization model [14]:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{(M-1)} \\
& \min \max_j \left\{ \left| \frac{w_B}{w_j} - a_{Bj} \right|, \left| \frac{w_j}{w_W} - a_{jW} \right| \right\} \\
& \text{s.t.} \quad \begin{cases} \sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1, \\ w_j \geq 0, \text{ for all } j = 1, 2, \dots, n. \end{cases}
\end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

Further, **(M-1)** can be transformed into the equivalent optimization model

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{(M-2)} \\
& \min \xi \\
& \text{s.t.} \quad \begin{cases} \left| \frac{w_B}{w_j} - a_{Bj} \right| \leq \xi \\ \left| \frac{w_j}{w_W} - a_{jW} \right| \leq \xi \\ \sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1, \\ w_j \geq 0, \text{ for all } j = 1, 2, \dots, n. \end{cases}
\end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

Solving the non-linear optimization model **(M-2)**, we can obtain optimal priority vector $w^* = (w_1^*, w_2^*, \dots, w_n^*)$.

3.1.2. Interval weight estimation approach

Rezaei [15] argued that in case of inconsistency with more than three objects the optimization model **(M-2)** might have multiple optimal solutions. To handle this issue, he proposed the idea of interval weight estimation. But Rezaei [15], did not provide any theoretical proof or evidence to support the existence of multiple optimal solutions.

In this approach, interval weight is derived from the pairwise comparison matrix following a two phases algorithm. In the first phase, **(M-1)** is solved to find the optimal value ξ^* , while the second phase involved finding the range of each weight component with ξ^* by solving the flowing optimization problem

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{(M-3)} \\
& \text{optimize } w_j \\
& \text{s.t.} \quad \begin{cases} \left| \frac{w_B}{w_j} - a_{Bj} \right| \leq \xi^* \\ \left| \frac{w_j}{w_W} - a_{jW} \right| \leq \xi^* \\ \sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1, \\ w_j \geq 0, \text{ for all } j = 1, 2, \dots, n. \end{cases}
\end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

By solving the model **(M-3)** for maximum and minimum of w_j , we can find the optimal interval priority

weight of the j -th object and similarly for the rest of the objects. Then, one can employ a probabilistic interval prioritization method to rank the objects and the centre value of the interval is considered as a representative of the weight of the object.

3.1.3. Relaxed linear model

Rezaei [15] proposed a linear model to compute the approximate priority weight of the objects without giving any proper justification/reason. The approximate priority weights w^* is obtained by solving the following linear optimization model:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{(M-4)} \\
 & \min \xi^L \\
 & \text{s.t.} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} w_B - a_{Bj}w_j \leq \xi^L \\ w_B - a_{Bj}w_j \geq -\xi^L \\ w_j - a_{jW}w_W \leq \xi^L \\ w_j - a_{jW}w_W \geq -\xi^L \\ \sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1, \\ w_j \geq 0, \text{ for all } j = 1, 2, \dots, n. \end{array} \right. \quad (5)
 \end{aligned}$$

The optimal value ξ^{L*} obtained by solving the model (M-4), considered as an indicator of the consistency of the given preference.

3.1.4. Multiplicative linear model

Brunelli and Rezaei [16] proposed a new metric, inspired from the abelian group theory of the pairwise comparison and claimed that the metric is more suitable with the multiplicative context of BWM than absolute value metric, which is more suitable for the additive framework. Using the *logarithmic* transformation $v_i = \ln w_i$, $b_{Bj} = \ln a_{Bj}$ and $b_{jW} = \ln a_{Bj}$, they propose the following mathematical model:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{(M-5)} \\
 & \min \xi \\
 & \text{s.t.} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} b_{Bj} - (v_B - v_j) = c_{Bj} - d_{Bj} \\ c_{Bj} + d_{Bj} \leq \xi \\ b_{jW} - (v_j - v_W) = e_{jW} - f_{jW} \\ e_{jW} + f_{jW} \leq \xi \\ \sum_{j=1}^n v_j = 0, \\ c_{Bj}, d_{Bj}, e_{jW}, f_{jW} \geq 0 \end{array} \right. \quad (6)
 \end{aligned}$$

Once we found the optimal solution of the model **(M-5)** in terms of the $v^* = (v_1^*, v_2^*, \dots, v_n^*)$, the transformation $w_j = e^{v_j}$ ($j = 1, 2, \dots, n$) is used to obtain the original weight followed by a normalization process.

3.2. Selection of the prioritization method

In the above, we have mentioned the four prioritization methods to find the weights from the reference comparisons with a numerical scale. It is quite reasonable that the different prioritization method may yield different results. Therefore, there is a need for appropriate selection criteria of the BWM prioritization methods. Among the suite of the criteria used to measure the performance of the prioritization methods, Euclidean distance (ED) is popular and widely used [32].

The key idea behind the ED based measure is that it computes the difference between the given pairwise comparisons and the derived priority weight obtained from the prioritization method. The Euclidean distance-based measure can be defined as follows:

$$ED = \sum_{j=1}^n \left(\frac{w_B}{w_j} - a_{Bj} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{w_j}{w_W} - a_{jW} \right)^2 \quad (7)$$

Based on the ED criteria, we attempt to evaluate the performance of the priority derivation models of the BWM. For that purpose, we consider the example illustrated by Rezaei [15]. A buyer of a car needs to prioritize five criteria for the selecting car: quality (C_1), price (C_2), comfort (C_3), safety (C_4) and style (C_5). For the buyer, price is the most important criteria, i.e., the best criteria while style is the less important criteria i.e., the worst criteria. The buyer provides the pairwise comparisons of the best-worst criteria with the others and that are summarized in the following pairwise comparison matrix:

$$P = \begin{matrix} & C_1 & C_B & C_3 & C_4 & C_W \\ \begin{matrix} C_1 \\ C_B \\ C_3 \\ C_4 \\ C_W \end{matrix} & \begin{pmatrix} - & - & - & - & 4 \\ 2 & 1 & 4 & 3 & 8 \\ - & - & - & - & 2 \\ - & - & - & - & 3 \\ - & - & - & - & 1 \end{pmatrix} \end{matrix}$$

Note that the given reference comparison P is not fully consistent. In the fully consistent case, it has been found that all the prioritization models produce the same weight vector. For this reason, we have considered the not fully consistent reference comparison to compare the performance of the prioritization methods. Now, the above-mentioned prioritization models are employed to find the priority weights from pairwise comparisons P and the results are summarized in Table I with the ED criteria.

Based on the ED measure criteria, it is evident from the Table I that the original non-linear model **(M-2)** of deriving priority weights has the least difference from the originally given preference while the priority weights derived from the multiplicative linear model **(M-5)** deviates significantly from the original

Table I: Comparison of the prioritization methods

prioritization model	w_1	w_2	w_3	w_4	w_5	ED
(M-2)	0.222499	0.451444	0.112463	0.158174	0.0554198	0.087262
(M-3)	0.221711	0.451634	0.113061	0.158241	0.055443	0.088095
(M-4)	0.229508	0.448087	0.114754	0.153005	0.0546448	0.186440
(M-5)	0.219722	0.457040	0.109861	0.158447	0.054931	0.263977

preference. Note that the given pairwise comparisons are almost fully consistent (when $a_{B4} = 2, a_{4W} = 4$ or $a_{B4} = 4, a_{4W} = 2$) and that might be the reason for the obtained priorities by all the methods are very close. To find the performance of prioritization methods under different level of inconsistency, we consider 9 pairwise comparisons matrices that are derived from the original preference matrix P by setting $a_{B4} = 2$ and $a_{4W} \in \{1, 2, \dots, 9\}$. Afterwards, all prioritization methods are employed to derive the priority weights in each case and subsequently, ED measures are computed. The performance of the prioritization methods concerning the ED measures is depicted in Figure 2. It has been observed that the non-linear model (M-2) produces the least deviation in all the considered inconsistent cases. Although, the performance of the interval weight estimation model (M-3) is very close to (M-2), there is a substantial difference. The prioritization processes (M-4) and (M-5) yield priority weights that deviate significantly from the original pairwise comparisons and produce unreliable results. In light of the above analysis, we are in the opinion that the non-linear prioritization method (M-2) produced more reliable results for the not fully consistent pairwise comparisons. Therefore, in this study, we adopt the non-linear prioritization method (M-2) to find weights of the objects.

Figure 2: ED measures for variation in evaluation

Remark 2. For solving (M-2)-(M-5), we have coded optimization models in *JuMP*¹ (Julia for Mathematical Programming) and called different solvers to find the optimal solutions. Specifically, the non-linear

¹<http://www.juliaopt.org/JuMP.jl/v0.13/>

optimization models are solved by calling *IPOPT*² solver (Interior Point OPTimizer) while the linear optimization models have been solved by calling *CPLEX* solver.

4. Linguistic best-worst method based on 2-tuple model

This section introduces the extension of BWM based on the 2-tuple linguistic model. First, the linguistic scale used by the decision makers to provide their preferences is defined in Section 4.1. The formalization of the best-worst pairwise comparison matrix is then provided in Section 4.2. The prioritization process to obtain the weights from linguistic information and their corresponding transformation into linguistic values is described in Sections 4.3. Afterwards, Section 4.4 introduces a re-translation function to calculate the deviation among the given preferences and the derived priority. Finally, the consistency ratio is defined in Sections 4.5 and 4.6.

4.1. Linguistic scale

In traditional BWM, '1-9' scale is used to provide decision maker's preference for the pairwise comparisons of the objects. But in many real-life DM scenarios, a decision maker needs to compare the objects associated with the complex concepts and the preference of the decision maker's involves subjectivity. In such scenarios, the quantification of the decision maker's preference with the precise numeric scale '1-9' is quite difficult. As the linguistic description is easily understood by human beings even when the context is abstract and complex, it is more convenient for the decision maker to express his/her preference in linguistic terms. In this view, we introduce the following linguistic term set as a linguistic scale for the BWM (see Fig. 3): $S^{BWM} = \{ l_1 = \text{Equally Preferred (EQ)}, l_2 = \text{Very Weakly Preferred (VWP)}, l_3 = \text{Weakly Preferred (WP)}, l_4 = \text{Moderately Preferred (MP)}, l_5 = \text{Fairly Preferred (FP)}, l_6 = \text{Moderate Strongly Preferred (MSP)}, l_7 = \text{Strongly Preferred (SP)}, l_8 = \text{Very Strongly Preferred (VSP)}, l_9 = \text{Extremely preferred (EP)} \}$.

Figure 3: Linguistic scale

Based on the linguistic term set S^{BWM} , the decision-maker could be able to provide the preference of the pairwise comparisons of the best and worst objects with the rest of the objects. The preference of the best object, x_B over any object x_j can take a value of linguistic term from the set S^{BWM} .

²<https://www.coin-or.org/Ipopt/documentation/>

Remark 3. Note that we have considered nine linguistic labels that are represented by the integers from $[1, 9]$ instead of $[0, 8]$. Therefore, we re-write the translation and re-translation functions as follows: $\Delta : [1, 9] \rightarrow S^{BWM} \times [-0.5, 0.5)$ and $\Delta^{-1} : S^{BWM} \times [-0.5, 0.5) \rightarrow [1, 9]$.

4.2. Formation of best-worst comparison matrix

Once the best and worst objects have been identified from the set of objects under consideration by the decision maker, the key issue in the decision process boils down to accumulate the preference information regarding the pairwise comparisons of the best and worst objects with the rest of the objects from the decision maker.

Given the linguistic term set, S^{BWM} with an associated 2-tuple computational model, the decision maker first compares the best object x_B with the rest of the objects $X \setminus \{x_B\}$ and expresses his/her assessments via a single linguistic term that are subsequently transformed into 2-tuple linguistic values (see Remark 1). The same has been done for the worst objects x_W . Decision maker's preference information can be summarized in the following linguistic best-worst pairwise comparison matrix (LBWPCM) with 2-tuple entries:

$$L = \begin{matrix} & x_1 & x_2 & \cdots & x_B & \cdots & x_W & \cdots & x_n \\ \begin{matrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ \vdots \\ x_B \\ \vdots \\ x_n \end{matrix} & \left(\begin{array}{ccccccccc} - & - & \cdots & - & \cdots & (d_{1W}, \alpha_{1W}) & \cdots & - \\ - & - & \cdots & - & \cdots & (d_{2W}, \alpha_{2W}) & \cdots & - \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \cdots & \vdots & \vdots & \cdots & \vdots \\ (d_{B1}, \alpha_{B1}) & (d_{B2}, \alpha_{B2}) & \cdots & - & \cdots & (d_{BW}, \alpha_{BW}) & \cdots & (d_{Bn}, \alpha_{Bn}) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \cdots & \vdots & \vdots & \cdots & \vdots \\ - & - & \cdots & - & \cdots & (d_{nW}, \alpha_{nW}) & \cdots & - \end{array} \right) \end{matrix}$$

where (d_{Bj}, α_{Bj}) is the linguistic preference of the decision maker against the comparison of the x_B with x_j and (d_{jW}, α_{jW}) denotes the linguistic preference for the comparison of x_W with x_j . It is evident that $d_{Bj}, d_{jW} \in S^{BWM}$ and $\alpha_{Bj}, \alpha_{jW} \in [-0.5, 0.5)$.

4.3. Finding the priority weights

After the decision maker completed the preference elicitation tasks by providing LBWPCM, we attempt to find the priority weights, which fit the given linguistic preference information optimally. Now, the optimal priority weights $w = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n)$ would be driven in such a way that the given preference for each object j should be preserved as much as possible. In other words, the optimal priority weights should satisfy the qualities $\frac{w_B}{w_j} = \Delta^{-1}((d_{Bj}, \alpha_{Bj}))$ and $\frac{w_j}{w_W} = \Delta^{-1}((d_{jW}, \alpha_{jW}))$ to some extent. This principle can be translated into a min-max optimization problem, where our objective is to minimize the maximum absolute difference $|\frac{w_B}{w_j} - \Delta^{-1}((d_{Bj}, \alpha_{Bj}))|$ and $|\frac{w_j}{w_W} - \Delta^{-1}((d_{jW}, \alpha_{jW}))|$ for all j . Therefore, the optimal priority

weights from the LBWPCM can be obtained by solving the non-linear optimization problem

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{(M-6)} \\
& \min \max_j \left\{ \left| \frac{w_B}{w_j} - \Delta^{-1}((d_{Bj}, \alpha_{Bj})) \right|, \left| \frac{w_j}{w_W} - \Delta^{-1}((d_{jW}, \alpha_{jW})) \right| \right\} \\
& \text{s.t.} \quad \begin{cases} \sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1, \\ w_j \geq 0, \text{ for all } j = 1, 2, \dots, n. \end{cases}
\end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

Finally, it can be transformed into minimization problem with non-linear objectives as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{(M-7)} \\
& \min \xi \\
& \text{s.t.} \quad \begin{cases} \sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1, \\ \left| \frac{w_B}{w_j} - \Delta^{-1}((d_{Bj}, \alpha_{Bj})) \right| \leq \xi, \\ \left| \frac{w_j}{w_W} - \Delta^{-1}((d_{jW}, \alpha_{jW})) \right| \leq \xi, \\ w_j \geq 0, \text{ for all } j = 1, 2, \dots, n. \end{cases}
\end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

Solving the optimization model (M-7), we can obtain the optimal priority weights $w^* = (w_1^*, \dots, w_n^*)$ and ξ^* .

However, the weights should be easily interpretable for the decision maker to understand the priority results in a natural language. In this vein, we introduce a linguistic term set (see Fig. 4), $S_1 = \{s_0 = \text{Very Unimportant (VU)}, s_1 = \text{Unimportant (U)}, s_2^1 = \text{Fair (F)}, s_3^1 = \text{Important (I)}, s_4^1 = \text{Very Important (VI)}\}$ and maps it to $[0, 1]$ via the re-translation step Δ_1^{-1} (see Def. 3). Further, we could able to interpret any value from the interval $\beta \in [0, 1]$ linguistically with help of translation operator $(\Delta_1(\cdot))$ (see Def. 2) as a priority weight of a particularly object under consideration.

Figure 4: Linguistic scale for weights

Definition 4. Let $w^* = (w_1^*, \dots, w_n^*)$ be the optimal priority weights (numeric) derived from (M-7). Then the corresponding 2-tuple linguistic optimal priority weights $l_{w^*} = (l_{w_1^*}, l_{w_2^*}, \dots, l_{w_n^*})$ such that $l_{w_j} \in \bar{S}_1 =$

$S_1 \times [-0.125, 0.125]$ can be obtained from numeric weight w^* as follows:

$$l_{w^*} = \Delta_1(w^*) = (\Delta_1(w_1^*), \Delta_1(w_2^*), \dots, \Delta_1(w_n^*)) \quad (10)$$

Remark 4. Note that the adaptation of the non-linear model to find the priority weights comes from the fact in Section 3.2 that the non-linear model produces the most reliable results than other comparative prioritization models.

Remark 5. Note that we have used a linguistic term set S_1 with cardinality $g_1 = 4$ in our proposal . However, the decision-maker could use any linguistic term set as long as its cardinality follows the psychologist recommendation that less than 5 terms being not sufficiently informative and more than 9 terms being too much for a proper understanding of their differences [33].

4.4. Re-translation function to analyse deviation from original opinions

By means of the prioritization process, we obtain the priority weights of the reference objects $w = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n)$ in the numerical scale $[0, 1]$ by preserving as much as possible the initial decision makers' preferences (see Section 3). Afterwards, they are subsequently transformed into the 2-tuple linguistic values $l_w = (l_{w_1}, l_{w_2}, \dots, l_{w_n})$ (see Section 4.3). However, decision makers cannot evaluate how much their initial linguistic preferences are preserved in the derived priority. To provide this information to the decision makers and facilitate the understanding over the prioritization weights, we apply a re-translation process that transforms the derived numerical prioritization weights into a LBWPCM. The resulting best-worst comparison preference employs the same linguistic scale used by the decision maker to give their assessments thus, he/she can evaluate easily the deviation among his/her preferences and the derived priority. For this purpose, we introduce a translation function, T such that

$$\bar{a}_{Bj} = T(w_B/w_j) = \begin{cases} \frac{w_B}{w_j} & \text{if } 1 \leq \frac{w_B}{w_j} \leq 9 \\ 1 & \text{if } \frac{w_B}{w_j} < 1 \\ 9 & \text{if } \frac{w_B}{w_j} > 9 \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

$$\bar{a}_{jW} = T(w_j/w_W) = \begin{cases} \frac{w_j}{w_W} & \text{if } 1 \leq \frac{w_j}{w_W} \leq 9 \\ 1 & \text{if } \frac{w_j}{w_W} < 1 \\ 9 & \text{if } \frac{w_j}{w_W} > 9 \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

The translation function T allows us to restore the original linguistic scale from the priority weights. By employing the original linguistic translation function $T(\cdot)$ on \bar{a}_{Bj} and \bar{a}_{jW} for all j , we can construct the LBWPCM \bar{L} , from the derived priority weight $w = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n)$. Therefore, the decision maker could easily compare the derived results \bar{L} and given linguistic preference L .

4.5. Consistency ratio for linguistic best-worst method

Even though it is expected that the decision maker will provide a fully consistent preference, the bounded rational behaviour of the decisionmaker yields inconsistency in the preference [34, 35]. Measuring such inconsistency in the given preferences of decision maker's is necessary for making a reliable choice. In this view, Rezaei [14] introduces the notion of consistency ratio (CR) that indicates how much the given preference is consistent. In order to check the consistency degree of LBWPCM, we extend the notion of CR in the 2-tuple linguistic environment by providing the definition of consistency and analogous concepts for LBWPCM as follows:

Definition 5. A given LBWPCM is said to be consistent if

$$\Delta^{-1}((d_{Bj}, \alpha_{Bj})) \times \Delta^{-1}((d_{jW}, \alpha_{jW})) = \Delta^{-1}(d_{BW}, \alpha_{BW}) \text{ for all } j \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}. \quad (13)$$

When the condition Eq. (13) does not hold for at least one j , we will say that the given LBWPCMM is not fully consistent or inconsistent. In this case, we compute the consistency ratio to measure the consistency degree.

In inconsistent scenarios, the violation of the Eq. (13) resulted the satisfaction of the inequalities $\Delta^{-1}((d_{Bj}, \alpha_{Bj})) \times \Delta^{-1}((d_{jW}, \alpha_{jW})) \leq \Delta^{-1}(d_{BW}, \alpha_{BW})$ for at least one j and that decreases the consistency degree of the LBWPCM. The possible highest value of the inequality occurs when $\Delta^{-1}((d_{Bj}, \alpha_{Bj}))$ and $\Delta^{-1}((d_{jW}, \alpha_{jW}))$ are equal to $\Delta^{-1}(d_{BW}, \alpha_{BW})$. Introducing a deviation variable, the inequity could be expressed as a equality as follows:

$$(\Delta^{-1}((d_{Bj}, \alpha_{Bj})) - \xi) \times (\Delta^{-1}((d_{jW}, \alpha_{jW})) - \xi) = (\Delta^{-1}(d_{BW}, \alpha_{BW}) - \xi) \quad (14)$$

When $\Delta^{-1}((d_{Bj}, \alpha_{Bj})) = \Delta^{-1}((d_{jW}, \alpha_{jW})) = \Delta^{-1}(d_{BW}, \alpha_{BW})$, the Eq. (14) transformed into

$$\xi^2 - (1 + 2\Delta^{-1}(d_{BW}, \alpha_{BW}))\xi + (\Delta^{-1}(d_{BW}, \alpha_{BW}))^2 - \Delta^{-1}(d_{BW}, \alpha_{BW}) = 0 \quad (15)$$

As $\Delta^{-1}(d_{BW}, \alpha_{BW}) \in [1, 9]$, we can find the maximal possible ξ by solving the Eq. (15). Further, one can use this maximum values of ξ as a consistency index and the corresponding consistency ratio of the LBWPCM will obtain as follows:

$$CR = \frac{\xi^*}{\text{Consistency Index}} \quad (16)$$

where ξ^* is obtained from the optimization model (M-6).

4.6. Random consistency measure

It has been observed that the maximum inconsistency in a given best-worst preference occurs when $a_{Bj} = a_{jW} = a_{BM}$ and the consistency ratio is the relative measure of the inconsistency concerning the

maximum inconsistency in $[0, 1]$ scale, where 0 indicates the perfect consistent scenario while 1 represents perfectly inconsistency scenario. However, such a notion of consistency is derived from the pessimistic view which may deviate significantly from decision makers' common cognitive behaviour. Further, there are no guidelines about the acceptable level of consistency.

Note that once decision maker fixed the best and worst objects with the ratio of the best to worst, the probability of occurring the maximal inconsistency depends not only the ratio a_{BW} but also on the number of objects under the consideration. For example, if there are 6 reference objects with $a_{BW} = l_6$, then the probability of the occurring the maximum inconsistency is $\frac{1}{6^6}$. When $a_{BW} = l_8$, the probability of occurring maximum inconsistency for the same scenario becomes $\frac{1}{8^6}$. Thus, the occurrence of the maximum inconsistency is a quite rare event. Due to this fact, we are going to introduce the notion of random consistency index (RCI) of the LBWPCM based on the average cognitive behaviour of the decision maker.

From a set of n reference objects, the decision maker first chooses the best and worst objects and selects a linguistic label to provide the preference for the best to worst object $a_{BW} = l_k$. The inconsistency in preference information may occur due to bounded rational behaviour in the rest of $2n - 4$ judgements. As $a_{BW} = l_k$, the rational decision maker will use the linguistic labels $\{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_k\}$ to fill up the rest of $2n - 4$ preference. With these choices, there are k^{2n-4} possible configurations of the decision maker's preferences consisting of both consistent and inconsistent preferences. Decision maker's preferences on the referenced objects will match with one of the configurations. We define the average consistency index as the mean of consistency of all possible configuration of preferences. However, when $n \geq 5$, the number of configurations k^{2n-4} becomes very large and finding average consistency index becomes a computationally tedious task. Keeping this fact in mind, we introduce the notion of *random average consistency index* (RACI), which defined as an average value of consistency ξ that are generated by selecting N configurations of the LBWPCMs for a given n and a_{BW} at random, i.e.

$$RACI(n, a_{BW}) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N \xi^{(k)}(n, a_{BW}) \quad (17)$$

where $\xi^{(k)}(n, a_{BW})$ is consistency of the k -th sample LBWPCM with best to worst preference a_{BW} . The consistency $\xi^{(k)}(n, a_{BW})$ is obtained by solving the optimization model **(M-7)**. Clearly, $RACI(n, a_{BW})$ can be viewed as an average cognitive inconsistency of the decision maker associated with LBWPCM. By setting up $N = 10,000$, we have computed $RACI(n, a_{BW})$ for different values of n and a_{BW} and the results are reported in the Table II. From Table II, it is evident that average cognitive behaviour of the decision makers $RACI(n, a_{BW})$ deviates significantly from the decision maker's extreme attitude, i.e. completely pessimistic view given by the decision maker. Moreover, Table II also depicts the phenomenon associated with human cognitive behaviour that with the increase of the number of choices inconsistency in the judgments gradually increases.

Based on the notion of $RACI(n, a_{BW})$, we re-define the consistency ratio for a given LBWPCM as

Table II: Average random consistency index

$RACI(n, a_{BW})$								
n	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
3	0.18361	0.37665	0.55037	0.75272	0.95964	1.18496	1.40357	1.64334
4	0.29530	0.54800	0.81162	1.09939	1.40172	1.71159	2.05341	2.40471
5	0.36089	0.64679	0.96388	1.30009	1.64452	2.04431	2.42486	2.848
6	0.40466	0.71746	1.06277	1.45598	1.84730	2.27373	2.71134	3.14877
7	0.43129	0.76699	1.14422	1.55603	1.98077	2.43942	2.90589	3.41465
8	0.44958	0.80825	1.20708	1.64420	2.09304	2.58759	3.07247	3.56621
9	0.77678	1.37058	2.00741	2.62732	3.27161	3.93522	4.67623	5.33078

follows:

$$CR(n, a_{BW}) = \frac{\xi(n, a_{BW})}{RACI(n, a_{BW})} \quad (18)$$

The new consistency ratio, defined by Eq. (18), can be viewed as a decision maker's cognitive deviation from the average rational decision makers' behaviour. The RACI index not only depends on the best to worst ratio a_{BW} but also on the number of the objects under consideration when the linguistic scale is fixed. This is the point of departure of our proposed RACI index from the Rezaei's proposal of consistency. Although one may feel that any value just below the RACI may sufficient to guarantee a reasonable consistency, practically that is not sufficient. Thus, we need to set a threshold to ensure the reasonable consistency in given reference comparison. It is needless to say that threshold with a value close to zero could ensure nearly-perfect consistency. But such conservative value may enforce the decision maker to behave near-perfect way and that could add cognitive bias. As there are a very few nearly-consistent reference comparisons for a given scale with a fixed best to worst ratio, this could be very high cognitively demanding to the decision maker. Thus, a value very close to zero may too restrictive while a larger value more than 0.5 would not be able to maintain a reasonable consistency. In fact, the primary random experiment with 5 reference objects and 1 – 9 scale indicates that the probability of generating a random reference comparison with consistency threshold 0.2 is near 0.0007 while for the threshold 0.35 it is about 0.0096. Further, in both of the cases the transitivity of the preferences are preserved. Based on these facts, we set $CR(n, a_{BW}) \leq 0.35$ as a consistency threshold, which is not very restrictive and guarantee sufficient consistency to generate reasonable results.

5. Optimal group formation with linguistic best-worst preferences

Classically, GDM framework has been adopted to obtain priority on a set of objects in BWMs, where a unique preference ranking is obtained by minimizing the deviation of the given preference information from the group of decision makers [36]. However, for instance, in LS-GDM problems, polarization in opinions and the identification of such polarized views need to be analyzed to understand properly the dynamics of groups with a large number of stakeholders/participants [9, 10].

In this section, we are interested to identify the formation of all sub-groups of decision makers based on the

coherence of their opinions. In particular, we aim to partition the group of decision makers into different sub-groups by minimizing the maximized deviation of the preference information given by each of the sub-groups of decision makers. This kind of settings will allow us to tackle the complex LS-GDM problems by relaxing the uniqueness of the preference ranking and allowing the partition among the different sub-groups. The critical distinction of our approach from the existing GDM based on the BWM is that our approach tries to come up with the multiple views according to the cohesion of each subgroup while the existing approach brute-force the formation of a single ranking from group preference.

To describe our approach mathematically, we introduce a few notations in the following. Let $\{DM_1, DM_2, \dots, DM_t\}$ be a group of decision makers. Each decision maker is characterized by his/her attitude, knowledge and expertise. Decision makers provide their linguistic preference over the objects using the linguistic term set S^{BWM} .

Each decision maker DM_k ($k = 1, 2, \dots, t$) first selects the best and worst objects from the set given objects and provides the preferences of best and worst objects over the set of objects. The preference of the k -th decision maker is summarized in the linguistic best-worst pair-wise comparison matrix, in short,

$$LBWPCM_k = \begin{matrix} & x_1 & x_2 & \cdots & x_B & \cdots & x_W & \cdots & x_n \\ \begin{matrix} x_B \\ x_W \end{matrix} & \begin{pmatrix} r_{B1}^k & r_{B2}^k & \cdots & r_{BB}^k & \cdots & r_{BW}^k & \cdots & r_{Bn}^k \\ r_{W1}^k & r_{W2}^k & \cdots & r_{WB}^k & \cdots & r_{WW}^k & \cdots & r_{Wn}^k \end{pmatrix} \end{matrix}$$

where, $r_{Bj}^k = (d_{Bj}^k, \alpha_{Bj}^k)$ with $d_{Bj}^k \in S^{BWM}$ and $\alpha_{Bj}^k \in [-0.5, 0.5]$.

We intend to divide the group of decision makers into p disjoint sub-groups by minimizing the sum of maximized deviation of the given preference information by each sub-groups. In this sequel, we introduce binary variables to capture the association of the decision makers to the sub-groups as follows:

$$y_{kg} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } k\text{-th decision maker belongs to } g\text{-th sub-group} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

Our interest is laying in finding the association decision variables y_{kg} , ($k = 1, 2, \dots, t$, $g = 1, 2, \dots, p$) with the numeric priority vector of the each sub-group $w^g = (w_1^g, w_2^g, \dots, w_n^g)$, ($g = 1, 2, \dots, p$) corresponding to the 2-tuple linguistic weight vector $l_{w_g} = (l_{w_1^g}, l_{w_2^g}, \dots, l_{w_n^g})$ ($g = 1, 2, \dots, p$) by minimizing the sum of maximized

deviation of the each sub-groups, which can be written as the following optimization problem:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{(M-8)} \\
& \min \sum_{g=1}^p \sum_{k=1}^t y_{kg} \max_j \left\{ \left| \frac{w_B^g}{w_j^g} - \Delta^{-1}((d_{Bj}^k, \alpha_{Bj}^k)) \right|, \left| \frac{w_j^g}{w_W^g} - \Delta^{-1}((d_{jW}^k, \alpha_{jW}^k)) \right| \right\} \\
& \text{s.t.} \begin{cases} \sum_{g=1}^p y_{kg} = 1, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, t \\ \sum_{k=1}^t y_{kg} \geq 1, \quad g = 1, 2, \dots, p \\ \sum_{j=1}^n w_j^g = 1, \quad g = 1, 2, \dots, p \\ w_j^g \geq 0, \quad \text{for all } j = 1, 2, \dots, n, g = 1, 2, \dots, p. \end{cases} \tag{20}
\end{aligned}$$

It is to be noted that in the optimization model **(M-8)**, the first and second set of constraints are required to form sub-groups of the decision makers. The first set of constraints dictated that each decision maker will be associated with exactly one sub-group, while the second set of constraints guaranteed that each sub-group will contain at least one decision maker. In the aim of simplifying the optimizing model **(M-8)**, we set

$$\xi_{kg} = \max_j \left\{ \left| \frac{w_B^g}{w_j^g} - \Delta^{-1}((d_{Bj}^k, \alpha_{Bj}^k)) \right|, \left| \frac{w_j^g}{w_W^g} - \Delta^{-1}((d_{jW}^k, \alpha_{jW}^k)) \right| \right\} \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, t, g = 1, 2, \dots, p$$

With this transformation, the optimization model **M-8** can be written as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{(M-9)} \\
& \min \sum_{g=1}^p \sum_{k=1}^t y_{kg} \xi_{kg} \\
& \text{s.t.} \begin{cases} \sum_{g=1}^p y_{kg} = 1, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, t \\ \sum_{k=1}^t y_{kg} \geq 1, \quad g = 1, 2, \dots, p \\ \left| \frac{w_B^g}{w_j^g} - \Delta^{-1}((d_{Bj}^k, \alpha_{Bj}^k)) \right| \leq \xi_{kg} \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, n, k = 1, 2, \dots, t, g = 1, 2, \dots, p \\ \left| \frac{w_j^g}{w_W^g} - \Delta^{-1}((d_{jW}^k, \alpha_{jW}^k)) \right| \leq \xi_{kg} \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, n, k = 1, 2, \dots, t, g = 1, 2, \dots, p \\ \sum_{j=1}^n w_j^g = 1, \quad g = 1, 2, \dots, p \\ w_j^g \geq 0, \quad \text{for all } j = 1, 2, \dots, n, g = 1, 2, \dots, p. \end{cases} \tag{21}
\end{aligned}$$

By solving the non-linear mixed-integer programming model, we can obtain the composition of each sub-groups with the priority weights, which will allow us to preference over the alternatives. Specifically, the part of the solution $\{y_{kg}^*\}$ gives us the association of the decision makers to different sub-groups and $w^{g*} = (w_1^{g*}, \dots, w_n^{g*})$ provides us the priority weights of the g -th sub-group. The corresponding 2-tuple linguistic weight vectors can obtained as follws: $l_{w^{g*}} = \Delta_1(w^{g*}) = (\Delta_1(w_1^{g*}), \Delta_1(w_2^{g*}), \dots, \Delta_1(w_n^{g*}))$.

Solving the mixed-integer non-linear programming (MINLP) model **(M-8)** for a large group (more than

30 decision makers [37]) is quite a daunting task. However, there are effective global optimization algorithms that have been widely used in solving industrial problems with a few hundreds of variables. However, their limited scalability restricted us to apply it in LS-GDM problems with thousands of variables. To this end, we use the recently developed solver JUNIPER [38] to obtain a solution of the MINLP model (M-9). The key advantage of the JUNIPER over other MINLP solvers is that it can find quickly high-quality feasible solutions without guarantees of global optimality [38].

The optimal value $\sum_{g=1}^p \sum_{k=1}^t y_{kg}^* \xi_{kg}^*$ indicates the total deviation of all the sub-groups preference from the original opinions of the decision maker under the optimal group partition configuration. This can be termed as a total inconsistency of the for the group configuration. The quantity $\sum_{k=1}^t y_{kg}^* \xi_{kg}^*$ denotes the total deviation of the members of the g -th sub-group original opinions from the derived g -th sub-group priority weights $(w_1^{g*}, w_2^{g*}, \dots, w_n^{g*})$. We will refer $\sum_{k=1}^t y_{kg}^* \xi_{kg}^*$ as the g -th sub-group inconsistency. The optimal value $\sum_{g=1}^p \sum_{k=1}^t y_{kg}^* \xi_{kg}^* = 0$ suggests that the members of the respective sub-groups provide fully consistent opinions. For a better understanding of the decision makers' on the aspect that how the derived preference deviate from their original linguistic preference, we can translate the priority weights $(w_1^{g*}, w_2^{g*}, \dots, w_n^{g*})$ into linguistic preference matrix according to methodology described in section 4.4 and present to the members of the g -th sub-group.

As consistency is vital to make reliable decision outcomes, the decision makers need to provide linguistic preference with reasonable consistency. To make sure that it is reasonable to measure the consistency of each decision maker via Eq. (16) before the commencement of the group formation process. Different sub-groups might have different levels of inconsistency. From the optimal decisions $\{\xi_{kg}^*\}$, we can define the RACI of the g -th sub-groups as follows:

$$CR^g = \max \left\{ \frac{\xi_{kg}^*}{RACI(n, a_{BW})} \mid \forall k \text{ with } y_{kg} = 1 \right\}.$$

Further, the inconsistency of the group can be defined from the inconsistency measures of the subgroups as follows: $CR = \max \{ CR^g : g = 1, 2, \dots, p \}$.

It is quite straightforward that for a fixed set of decision makers there exists a lot of different configuration of the group, which can be detected by varying the index of the number of sub-groups p . We could use the inconsistency indexes, defined above to evaluate the different configuration of the group to find the most appropriate configuration.

Remark 6. When $p = 1$, i.e., there is no partition among the group of decision makers, the group priority weight-driven optimization model (M-8) translates into the best-worst GDM model proposed by Safarzadeh et al.[36] under the assumption that each decision maker's opinion is equally important in the formation of the group opinion.

Remark 7. For a fixed set of decision makers (t), we may interested to check different configurations of the

group by varying the number of sub-groups (i.e., p). With the increment of a single sub-group, we add t more binary variables (y_{kg}) to our GDM model (M-8) and that increase the complexity.

6. Practical examples

In order to show the usefulness and validity of the novel version of BWM based on the 2-tuple linguistic model, this section introduces two different examples. The former describes a simple real DM problem in which just a single expert participates in the decision process. The latter introduces an LS-GDM problem in which a large number of experts participate in the decision process. Both examples will be solved with the proposed BWM, by obtaining the weights of the criteria and, to conclude, the ranking of the alternatives.

6.1. Classical decision-making example

Suppose a travel agency wants to acquire a set of cars for their business. After initial screening they have shortlisted four cars, say $X = \{x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4\}$, as a possible options for the acquisition. Specification of these cars collected from the dealers and pass to the key decision maker to compare the cars.

To prioritize the cars according to the linguistic best-worst method, the decision maker is required to identify the best and worst cars from X considering the company's key perspectives. Based on the specification of the cars, the decision maker found that the best car is x_2 and x_4 is the worst one.

Once the best and worst cars have been identified, the decision maker makes pairwise comparisons among C_B and C_W with the rest of the alternatives. In order to facilitate the elicitation of the preferences, the decision maker expresses his/her assessments making use of the linguistic scale introduced in Section 4.1, The comparisons are shown in Tables III and IV:

Table III: Best alternative comparisons.

The best car	x_1	x_2	x_3	x_4
x_3	VWP	WP	-	VSP

Table IV: Worst alternative comparisons.

The worst car	x_4
x_1	FP
x_2	WP
x_3	VSP
x_4	-

The linguistic best-worst preference of the decision maker can be transformed into 2-tuple linguistic best-worst preference matrix as follows:

$$L = \begin{matrix} & x_1 & x_2 & x_3 & x_4 \\ x_3 & (l_2, 0) & (l_3, 0) & (l_1, 0) & (l_8, 0) \\ x_4 & (l_5, 0) & (l_3, 0) & (l_8, 0) & (l_1, 0) \end{matrix}$$

Now, we employ the model **(M-7)** to derive the priority weights from L and obtain 2-tuple linguistic priority weights $l_w^* = ((U, 0.03), (VU, -0.079), (F, 0.239), (VU, -0.19))$ with $\xi^* = 0.25834$. From Eq. (18), it is found that the consistency ratio for the given linguistic preferences is $CR(4, 8) = 0.3184$, which indicates that the given preference information is consistent enough to find a reasonable result. The 2-tuple linguistic weight is easily understandable to the decision maker as a linguistic description is much easier to interpret than a numeric one.

Model **(M-7)** obtains priority weights by preserving as much as possible the decision maker's initial preferences (see Section. 3). However, in order to the buyer also knows the deviation of his/her initial preferences regarding the resulting weights, we further transform the derived numeric priority weights i.e., $\Delta_1^{-1}(l_w^*)$ into linguistic best-worst preference information by utilizing Eqs. (11) and (12) as follows:

$$\bar{L} = \begin{matrix} & x_1 & x_2 & x_3 & x_4 \\ x_3 & (l_2, -0.26) & (l_3, -0.13) & (l_1, 0) & (l_8, 0.25) \\ x_4 & (l_5, -0.26) & (l_3, -0.13) & (l_8, 0) & (l_1, 0.25) \end{matrix}$$

As the prioritization weights are translated into the given preference information format employing 2-tuple linguistic values, which keeps the initial linguistic terms used by the buyer to provide their assessments, by means of the comparison between L and \bar{L} , the buyer can easily check how his/her given information is preserved by the derived priority weights. Such comparison, in turn, facilitates the interpretation of the weights.

To conclude, a ranking of the alternatives is obtained (see Table V). According to the preferences of the decision maker, the ranking order of the car is $x_3 \succ x_1 \succ x_2 \succ x_4$.

Table V: Ranking of the alternatives.

Car	Ranking
x_1	2
x_2	3
x_3	1
x_4	4

6.2. Comparison with fuzzy best-worst method

To compare our approach with the fuzzy BWM, we have adopted an example from Guo and Zhao [17], which considers the selection of the transportation mode based on the three criteria: load flexibility (C_1), accessibility (C_2) and cost (C_3) and aims to find the appropriate weights of the criteria. The criteria are compared with the best and worst criteria by using the fuzzy linguistic scale given in Table VI and comparisons are summarized in the Tables VII and VIII.

Now, we employ the fuzzy BWM and reported the approximated weight obtained from the fuzzy weights by using graded mean integration representation in Table IX. We further obtained the result for the same

Table VI: Fuzzy linguistic terms with membership function

Linguistic terms	membership function
Equally importance (EI)	(1, 1, 1)
Weakly important (WI)	(2/3, 1, 3/2)
Fairly important (FI)	(3/2, 2, 5/2)
Very important (VI)	(5/2, 3, 7/2)
Absolutely important (AI)	(7/2, 4, 9/2)

Table VII: Linguistic fuzzy comparisons best criteria to others

Best criteria	C_1	C_2	C_3
C_3	AI	WI	-

prioritization problem with the proposed 2-tuple BWM by using five linguistic terms of Table VI and reported in Table IX (see Fig. 5). From Table IX, it is clear that both the approaches produced almost similar weights of the criteria. However, the weights of the proposed 2-tuple linguistic information expressed in a 2-tuple linguistic form which is easily interpretable to the decision maker than the numerical one in the fuzzy best-worst method.

Figure 5: 2-tuple weights

6.3. Large-scale group decision making problem

Let us suppose a group of 50 entrepreneurs who have decided to make a donation to help the development of their hometown. Such donation is intended for the construction of a sustainable building, being four the possible options, $X = \{x_1 : hospital, x_2 : shopping\ center, x_3 : feeding\ centre, x_4 : school, x_5 : vocational\ training\ center\}$. To make this complex decision, the entrepreneurs consider the follow aspects to make comparisons among the possible options:

- *Investment*: the total amount of money needed to carry out the construction of the building.
 - *Opinion of the inhabitants*: the inhabitants of the city will be asked about their preferences.
 - *Place*: depending of the building, the construction will be carried out in different places of the city.
- The aim is to avoid harming citizens as little as possible during the construction of the building.

Table VIII: Linguistic fuzzy comparisons worst criteria to others

worst criteria	C_1
C_1	-
C_2	FI
C_3	AI

Table IX: Weight obtained by different approaches

Method	weights
Fuzzy BWM	(0.1431, 0.3496, 0.5073)
2-tuple linguistic BWM	$((VU, -0.1111), (U, 0.0643), (F, 0.0746))$

- *Socio-economic impact*: it is intended that the new building leads to a social and economic benefit for the city.

The entrepreneurs are asked to select the best and worst investment options and to provide preferences over best to others and worst to others by using the linguistic term set S^{BW} . For sake of space, the selection of the best and worst options and their comparisons with the rest of the options for each entrepreneur have been included in Appendix A. We aim to identify the formation of the consistent sub-groups from the given best-worst preference information.

First, we check the consistency of each entrepreneur’s preference. For this purpose, we computed the relative consistency as defined in Eq. (18). The distribution of relative consistency has been depicted in Fig. 6. There is reasonable consistency in the given opinions by the entrepreneurs as the maximum CR is less than 0.34.

Figure 6: Distribution of the entrepreneurs’ RACI

We intend to analyze the compositions of the groups for different values of the k , the number of sub-groups. Specifically, we vary k in the set $\{1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$. For each of the values of k , we solve the model (M-9) by using JUNIPER solvers to find the compositions of the groups. Specifically, we coded the optimization model (M-9) in JuMp version 0.18 and invoked the JUNIPER solver to find the results to (M-9) reported in this paper. Note that in JUNIPER solver configuration, the NLP solver Ipopt is used for solving the continuous relaxation sub-problems and the MIP solver Cbc is used in the feasibility pump heuristic. The

variation of the objectives for the different values of the k has been depicted in Fig. 7 . In the trivial case, i.e., $k = 1$, the inconsistency in the group is quite high in comparison to other cases and that indicates a larger degree of disagreement in the group. In fact, there is a significant drop in objectives from $k = 1$ to $k = 2$ and this fact indicates the presence of more than one group among the decision makers as there is sufficient conflict among the decision makers opinions.

Figure 7: The value of the objectives (total group inconsistencies) obtained by JUNIPER for different values of $k=\{1,2,3,4,5,6\}$

Now, we are going to look into the compositions of the different group structures. For the different values of $k \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$, we report configurations (Fig. 8) of the different groups with each sub-groups total inconsistencies and cardinality in Table X. We label the sub-groups as G_1, G_2, G_3 and G_4 . For $k = 2$, the total inconsistencies have reduced significantly. The group is divided into two sub-groups with equal numbers of entrepreneurs and each sub-group has almost the same internal inconsistency. Further, average inconsistency level for the subgroup G_1 , i.e. total inconsistencies/cardinality of the subgroup 0.6640 and for G_2 , 0.716 are considerably decreased from the single group scenario. When $k = 3$, the total inconsistency is not much differ from the case $k = 2$ and entrepreneurs are almost equally distributed among the sub-groups $\{G_1, G_2, G_3\}$. The sub-group G_2 is more consistent than the sub-groups G_1 and G_3 . For $k = 4$, the total inconsistency reduces by more than 7% from the case $k = 3$. In fact, the internal coherence of the sub-groups increases. In a nutshell, all the evidence support that it is reasonable to partition the group into at least two subgroups of the decision makers.

Figure 8: Group configuration for different values of k

Table X: Inconsistencies and cardinality of the groups

k	G_1		G_2		G_3		G_4	
	inconsistency	cardinality	inconsistency	cardinality	inconsistency	cardinality	inconsistency	cardinality
1	47.7	50	-	-	-	-	-	-
2	16.6	25	17.9	25	-	-	-	-
3	12.57	17	7.5	16	14.29	17	-	-
4	10.543	15	6.17	12	5.39	11	9.72	12

Let us now analyze the priorities of the alternatives exhibited by the different configurations of the groups of entrepreneurs. For the $k = 1$, we obtain the 2-tuple linguistic priority weights $l_w^* = ((U, -0.0423), (VU, -0.158), (U, -0.004), (U, -0.0423), (U, -0.004))$. Further the corresponding numeric weight $\Delta_1^{-1}(l_w^*)$ can be transformed into linguistic best-worst preference information by utilizing Eqs. (11) and (12) to understand the deviation from original preference of the decision makers as follows:

$$\bar{L}^{k=1} = \begin{matrix} & & x_1 & & x_2 & & x_3 & & x_4 & & x_5 \\ x_3/x_5 & \left(\begin{matrix} (l_1, 0.19) & (l_3, -0.333) & (l_1, 0) & (l_1, 0.19) & (l_1, 0) \\ (l_2, 0.25) & (l_1, 0) & (l_3, -0.333) & (l_2, 0.25) & (l_3, -0.333) \end{matrix} \right) \\ x_4 & & & & & & & & & & \end{matrix}$$

It is evident to the entrepreneurs that group decision deviates significantly from their original opinions. Further, we obtain partial order of the alternatives from the priorities w^* that has been reported in the Table XI against the column $k = 1$, where there is a tie between x_3 and x_5 for the choice of most suitable option. When $k = 2$, we obtain the 2-tuple linguistic priority weights for the two sub-groups G_1 and G_2 as follows: $l_w^{g1*} = ((F, -0.101), (VU, 0.069), (U, -0.0904), (U, -0.0577), (U, -0.0697))$ and $l_w^{g2*} = ((U, -0.123), (VU, 0.059), (U, -0.0466), (U, -0.0975), (F, -0.0424))$. Translating the corresponding numeric priority vectors $\Delta_1^{-1}(l_w^{g1*})$ and $\Delta_1^{-1}(l_w^{g2*})$ into decision maker's linguistic best-worst preference format, we have

$$\bar{L}^{g1} = \begin{matrix} & & x_1 & & x_2 & & x_3 & & x_4 & & x_5 \\ x_1 & \left(\begin{matrix} (l_1, 0) & (l_6, -0.21) & (l_3, -0.5) & (l_2, 0.073) & (l_2, 0.21) \\ (l_6, -0.21) & (l_1, 0) & (l_2, 0.31) & (l_3, -0.21) & (l_3, -0.38) \end{matrix} \right) \\ x_2 & & & & & & & & & & \end{matrix}$$

$$\bar{L}^{g2} = \begin{matrix} & & x_1 & & x_2 & & x_3 & & x_4 & & x_5 \\ x_5 & \left(\begin{matrix} (l_4, -0.41) & (l_8, -0.29) & (l_2, 0.25) & (l_3, 0) & (l_1, 0) \\ (l_2, 0.14) & (l_1, 0) & (l_3, 0.43) & (l_3, -0.43) & (l_8, -0.29) \end{matrix} \right) \\ x_2 & & & & & & & & & & \end{matrix}$$

From \bar{L}^{g1} and \bar{L}^{g2} , we found sufficient agreement among the decision makers of the respective group. Further, from the priority weights, we found the complete order of the alternatives for the respective groups and reported in Table XI against the column $k = 2$. Setting up a hospital (x_1) is the best option among the members of the group G_1 , while members of G_2 preferred vocational training centre (x_5) over other options. Clearly, there is a polarization among the subgroups G_1 and G_2 , where members of G_1 think that better healthcare facility is the key determinant factor for the sustainable development of the community while members of G_2 feel that preparing youth for the jobs through vocational training is the most factor to

Table XI: Ordering of the alternatives for the different configuration of groups

the sustainable development of the community. Similarly, we obtain the ordering of the possible community development for the values of $k = 3$ and $k = 4$ and report it in Table XI. The ranking results suggest the division of the decision makers' into different homogeneous sub-groups.

7. Conclusions

In this study, we have investigated the classical prioritization method, best-worst, in the light of linguistic fuzzy information by adopting 2-tuple linguistic computational model, which enhanced the interpretability of the linguistic fuzzy approach with the concept of symbolic translation. For the facilitation of the reference comparisons for the best and worst objects with other objects, we have defined a linguistic term set which has utilized by decision makers to complete the linguistic best-worst pairwise comparison matrix. The priority weight of the objects from the linguistic best-worst pairwise comparison matrix has been obtained by solving the non-linear optimization model because of its superiority in comparisons to the other prioritization methods that have been established through numerical experiments. To present the priority weights into decision maker's understandable format, i.e., in terms of linguistic information, we have proposed a re-translation function that allows decision maker to understand and interpret easily the priority of the objects. To address the consistency and reliability issue of the given linguistic best-worst preference, we have introduced the notion of a new consistency ratio based on the idea of how far the decision maker cognitively deviates from the average cognitive behaviour of the decision maker. Afterwards, we have investigated the optimal configuration of the group based on the coherence of the decision makers opinions, given via linguistic best-worst preference and formulated a non-linear mixed integer programming problem to identify such configurations of the group, where each sub-groups agreed unanimously on a ranking order of the objects. With the help of didactic examples, we have illustrated the working and demonstrated the applicability of the proposed methodology.

The key advantages of the proposed methodology can be pointed out as follows: 1) the adaptation of 2-tuple computational model and the proposed re-translation of the weight in the form linguistic information equivalent to the decision maker original opinion enhance the accuracy and interpretability of the linguistic

best-worst method; 2) the proposed consistency ratio offers a better understating of the measure inconsistency in terms of average cognitive behaviour than the original pessimistic approach of measuring consistency; 3) the proposed group configuration identifying approach is capable of detecting multiple views within the group according to the cohesion of the subgroups.

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Appendix A. Large-scale data example

Table A.12: Decision makers' comparisons

		Hospital	Shopping center	Feeding center	School	Vocational training center
DM_1	BO	EQ	EP	VWP	VWP	MP
	WO	EP	EQ	SP	WP	VWP
DM_2	BO	MP	SP	WP	EQ	VWP
	WO	VWP	EQ	VWP	SP	VWP
DM_3	BO	EQ	SP	MP	MSP	VWP
	WO	SP	EQ	VWP	VWP	WP
DM_4	BO	EP	EP	EQ	VWP	SP
	WO	VWP	EQ	EP	EP	VWP
DM_5	BO	WP	SP	MSP	FP	EQ
	WO	VWP	EQ	VWP	VWP	SP
DM_6	BO	EQ	VSP	WP	SP	MSP
	WO	VSP	EQ	VWP	VWP	VWP
DM_7	BO	VWP	EP	VWP	MP	EQ
	WO	MSP	EQ	MP	WP	EP
DM_8	BO	MSP	EP	MP	VWP	EQ
	WO	VWP	EQ	WP	VSP	EP
DM_9	BO	WP	VSP	WP	MP	EQ
	WO	MP	EQ	WP	WP	VSP
DM_{10}	BO	VWP	SP	EQ	WP	WP
	WO	MSP	EQ	SP	WP	WP
DM_{11}	BO	FP	VSP	VWP	VWP	EQ
	WO	VWP	EQ	WP	MP	VSP
DM_{12}	BO	WP	SP	VWP	VWP	EQ
	WO	VWP	EQ	FP	MP	SP
DM_{13}	BO	FP	EP	EQ	MSP	EP
	WO	WP	EQ	EP	VWP	VWP
DM_{14}	BO	EQ	EP	VWP	MP	VWP
	WO	EP	EQ	MP	VWP	VSP
DM_{15}	BO	MP	VSP	WP	EQ	MSP
	WO	WP	EQ	MP	VSP	VWP

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Table A.12 – continued from previous page

		Hospital	Shopping center	Feeding center	School	Vocational training center
DM_{16}	BO	EQ	EP	FP	VWP	VWP
	WO	EP	EQ	WP	MP	VSP
DM_{17}	BO	WP	EP	EQ	MP	WP
	WO	MP	EQ	EP	WP	WP
DM_{18}	BO	EQ	EP	MSP	EP	VWP
	WO	EP	EQ	VWP	VWP	EP
DM_{19}	BO	EQ	VSP	MP	MP	MSP
	WO	VSP	EQ	WP	WP	VWP
DM_{20}	BO	VWP	SP	WP	VWP	EQ
	WO	FP	EQ	VWP	MSP	SP
DM_{21}	BO	SP	VSP	MP	VWP	EQ
	WO	VWP	EQ	WP	WP	VSP
DM_{22}	BO	MSP	EP	EQ	MP	MP
	WO	VWP	EQ	EP	VWP	VWP
DM_{23}	BO	VWP	SP	VWP	VWP	EQ
	WO	WP	EQ	MSP	MSP	SP
DM_{24}	BO	EQ	VSP	VWP	WP	MP
	WO	VSP	EQ	VWP	VWP	VWP
DM_{25}	BO	FP	EP	EQ	FP	VWP
	WO	WP	EQ	EP	WP	VSP
DM_{26}	BO	SP	VSP	VWP	SP	EQ
	WO	VWP	EQ	SP	VWP	VSP
DM_{27}	BO	EQ	EP	FP	VWP	MSP
	WO	EP	EQ	VWP	MP	VWP
DM_{28}	BO	WP	VSP	WP	VWP	EQ
	WO	MP	EQ	WP	MSP	VSP
DM_{29}	BO	VSP	EP	FP	EQ	VWP
	WO	VWP	EQ	VWP	EP	EP
DM_{30}	BO	WP	SP	MP	WP	EQ
	WO	WP	EQ	VWP	VWP	SP
DM_{31}	BO	MSP	VSP	VWP	VWP	EQ
	WO	VWP	EQ	SP	FP	VSP

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Table A.12 – continued from previous page

		Hospital	Shopping center	Feeding center	School	Vocational training center
DM_{32}	BO	VWP	SP	VWP	EQ	VWP
	WO	WP	EQ	MSP	SP	MP
DM_{33}	BO	EQ	VSP	VWP	MP	WP
	WO	VSP	EQ	FP	WP	WP
DM_{34}	BO	EQ	VSP	VWP	WP	VWP
	WO	VSP	EQ	WP	VWP	FP
DM_{35}	BO	WP	EP	EP	EQ	WP
	WO	FP	EQ	VWP	EP	MP
DM_{36}	BO	VWP	EP	EQ	MP	FP
	WO	MP	EQ	EP	WP	WP
DM_{37}	BO	EQ	SP	WP	WP	WP
	WO	SP	EQ	WP	WP	VWP
DM_{38}	BO	FP	EP	MP	EQ	EP
	WO	VWP	EQ	VWP	EP	VWP
DM_{39}	BO	WP	VSP	EQ	FP	VWP
	WO	MP	EQ	VSP	SP	MP
DM_{40}	BO	WP	VSP	VWP	MP	EQ
	WO	VWP	EQ	MP	WP	VSP
DM_{41}	BO	SP	SP	VWP	EQ	WP
	WO	WP	EQ	MP	SP	WP
DM_{42}	BO	EP	EP	EP	EQ	MP
	WO	VWP	EQ	VWP	EP	VWP
DM_{43}	BO	VWP	EP	EQ	VWP	VWP
	WO	MSP	EQ	EP	FP	VSP
DM_{44}	BO	MP	EP	WP	FP	EQ
	WO	VWP	EQ	WP	WP	EP
DM_{45}	BO	WP	VSP	MSP	VWP	EQ
	WO	MP	EQ	VWP	MSP	VSP
DM_{46}	BO	EQ	VSP	FP	VWP	MP
	WO	VSP	EQ	VWP	SP	VWP
DM_{47}	BO	EQ	EP	WP	MP	MP
	WO	EP	EQ	MP	VWP	WP

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Table A.12 – continued from previous page

		Hospital	Shopping center	Feeding center	School	Vocational training center
<i>DM</i> ₄₈	BO	WP	SP	VWP	VWP	EQ
	WO	WP	EQ	MP	FP	SP
<i>DM</i> ₄₉	BO	VWP	VSP	FP	MP	EQ
	WO	FP	EQ	VWP	VWP	VSP
<i>DM</i> ₅₀	BO	EQ	VSP	WP	VWP	WP
	WO	VSP	EQ	VWP	FP	WP